

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

FAMILIES RAISING CHILDREN WITH DISABILITIES AS AN OBJECT OF PSYCHOLOGICAL RESEARCH

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Abstract

Working with families raising children with disabilities is one of the most difficult problems of modern psychology. Until recently, such families were not the object of special study, and software and methodological support for their maintenance was not developed. The problem of educating and adapting such children to society came to the fore, while the psychological problems of the children themselves, and especially their families, faded into the background. It should be taken into account that the physiological problems of such children interfere with their normal socialization and turn into psychological problems of the child himself and his family.

Keywords: families, children with disabilities, inquiry, disability theory,

The family is a micro society in which the child not only lives, but in which his moral qualities, attitude to the world of people, ideas about the nature of interpersonal and social relations are formed. The family is considered as a backbone determinant in the socio-cultural status of the child, predetermining his further psychophysical and social development. Modern studies have revealed a direct dependence of the influence of the family factor on the characteristics of the development of the child: the stronger the manifestation of family trouble, the more pronounced developmental disorders in the child (B.P. Nikishina, 2004). These provisions should be taken into account both in diagnostic and remedial work with a child with developmental disorders [1].

The implementation of psychological assistance to families allows, through the optimization of the intra-family atmosphere, the harmonization of interpersonal, marital, parent-child and child-parent relationships, to solve the problems of differentiated and targeted assistance to a child with developmental disabilities.

Various forms of education both in state and non-state educational institutions, work with children with pronounced psychophysical disabilities include such a family in the field of correctional and pedagogical influence as the main stabilizing factor in the social adaptation of the child [2].

The need for special psychological assistance to families raising children with developmental disabilities arises from the huge number of various problems that these families encounter on a daily basis. The creation of a favorable rehabilitation and correctional-learning environment for the child during his stay at home is of the utmost importance. This requires a certain amount of knowledge from parents, helping to understand the needs and abilities of the child. They must also possess practical skills that allow them to method-

ically communicate with the child correctly and educate him correctly [3].

Psych correctional work can also provide significant assistance to parents of children with developmental disabilities. Parents need special help to neutralize those psychological problems that arise as a result of their personal experiences associated with developmental disorders of the child. Of particular importance are the personal characteristics of the parent, his attitude to abnormal development as a whole, when determining the nature and content of his contacts with his own child with psychophysical disorders. So, the provision of psychological assistance to families allows you to optimize the problems of a personal and interpersonal nature that arise as a result of the birth of a child with disabilities in the family. The main goal in this work is to change the parent's self-awareness, namely: the formation of a positive perception of the personality of a child with developmental disabilities. Such a position will allow the parent to find a new meaning in life, harmonize relationships with the child, increase their own self-esteem, optimize self-awareness. This, in turn, will direct parents to the use of harmonious models of education, and in the long term will ensure the optimal social adaptation of the child [4].

Children with disabilities are children with various mental or physical deviations that cause violations of general development that do not allow children to lead a full life.

According to the classification proposed by V.A. Lapshin and B.P. Puzanov, the main categories of children with disabilities include:

1. Children with hearing impairment (deaf, hard of hearing, late deaf);
2. Children with visual impairment (blind, visually impaired);
3. Children with speech disorders (logo paths);
4. Children with disorders of the musculoskeletal

system;

5. Children with mental retardation;
6. Children with mental retardation;
7. Children with behavioral and communication disorders;

Children with complex disorders of psychophysical development, with so-called complex defects (deaf-blind, deaf or blind children with mental retardation) [5].

In foreign psychology, the problems of families raising children with disabilities are not considered as a separate block. All these problems are considered within the framework of various approaches of family psychotherapy, which in turn are based on different areas of psychology:

- classical Freudianism (S. Freud, J. Breuer, J. Lacan, S. Ferenczi, C. Abraham, E. Glover);
- analytical psychology (K. G. Jung);
- humanistic psychology (K. Horney, K. Rogers, A. Adler, E. Fromm);
- behavioral psychotherapy (J. Watson, J. Wolpe, M. and K. Jones, E. Thorndike, G. Eysenck, E. Salter)
- rational-emotional psychotherapy (A. Ellis), etc.

The basic postulates of classical Freudianism are well known and do not need to be repeated. Currently, classical psychoanalysis is considered an outdated approach, however, in all Western countries, there are still schools of psychoanalysis that work with clients based on the analysis of their dreams, unconscious fears, repressed sexual desires using hypnosis techniques [5].

Currently, research on the possibilities of psycho-

logical support for families with children with disabilities is being actively developed. One of the areas of psychological assistance to such families is the psychological support of a family raising a child with disabilities.

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